

Splitflow: A Python Library for Efficient Distributed Data Analysis

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Abstract— This paper introduces Splitflow, a Python library created for the distributed processing of dataframes, focusing on a novel column-oriented methodology. Splitflow distinguishes itself by offering an innovative solution to the challenges posed by the vast volumes of data. The library's architecture is explored in detail, emphasizing its design principles that prioritize efficient data segmentation and user-defined trimming of columns. A comprehensive set of column-centric methods, including statistical analyses and exploratory data operations, empowers users with a versatile toolkit for diverse data analysis tasks. The paper presents a thorough comparative assessment of alternative libraries. The paper underscores Splitflow's adaptability and utility in solving complex data challenges. This paper is a practical guide, empowering users to leverage Splitflow for streamlined and effective distributed dataframe processing. Splitflow emerges as a pivotal tool, propelling the evolution of contemporary data analysis in Python.

Keywords— Python library, Distributed processing, Dataframes, Column-oriented, Data segmentation, User-defined trimming, Performance evaluation, Scalability, Comparative analysis, Machine learning, Business intelligence, Performance metrics, Versatile toolkit, Exploratory data analysis, Large datasets, Statistical analysis, Data exploration, Resource utilization, Efficiency, MapReduce operations, Duplicate identification, User-defined functions, Library comparison, Data analytics, Data manipulation, Parallelization

I. INTRODUCTION

As technology progresses, the exponential daily growth of data volumes has become a significant challenge across various industries. To address this challenge, the Splitflow Python library has emerged as a noteworthy solution for the distributed processing of dataframes. Meticulously crafted, Splitflow revolutionizes the conventional handling of CSV files, providing a streamlined solution for managing and processing large datasets. At its core, Splitflow introduces a novel mechanism for breaking substantial CSV files into smaller, more manageable chunks. These intelligently organized fragments are stored within a designated 'data folder'. Notably, the system efficiently navigates through these fragmented datasets using indexes, facilitating seamless retrieval and analysis of data based on specific slices. This paper delves into the intricate workings of splitflow, exploring its architecture, design principles, and implementation. Through implementation guides and performance evaluations, we seek to demonstrate the significance of splitflow in the contemporary landscape of Python data analysis tools.

II. ARCHITECTURE AND DESIGN OF SPLITFLOW

Splitflow's architecture revolves around a distinctive column-oriented paradigm, providing a specialized approach to distributed dataframe processing. This section delves into the key components and design principles that underpin the effectiveness of Splitflow as a versatile tool for data analysis.

Splitflow's core strength lies in its ability to segment large CSV files into smaller, manageable chunks. This process is fundamentally column-oriented, where the library separates columns and trims them to user-specified sizes. At the heart of Splitflow are its column-centric methods, each tailored for specific analytical tasks. The library boasts an extensive array of methods, including `mean()`, `mode()`, `median()`, `count()`, `value_count()`, `column_values()`, `find()`, `values()`, `duplicates()`, `count_duplicates()` and `MapRed()`. These methods collectively empower users to perform diverse analytical operations. Splitflow automatically generates a default folder named 'data' to house the segmented CSV files upon usage. Simultaneously, an `index.csv` file facilitates seamless navigation through the 'data' folder, allowing users to retrieve specific data slices efficiently—Splitflow's design centres around harnessing the power of column-specific functions. The library optimizes data manipulation operations by focusing on individual columns, ensuring efficiency and precision in deriving meaningful insights during analyses. The operations on the

data are performed in a distributed fashion concurrently based on [6] and [7] to ensure fast and efficient performance.

Fig. 1 Folder architecture of folder created by Splitflow

Upon the generation of the data folder derived from a larger dataset, it comprises two essential components: the data CSV files and the index.csv file. These components play a pivotal role in navigating and managing the dataset effectively. The data CSV files within the folder are generated based on specified data split values. These values are instrumental in partitioning the extensive dataset into more manageable subsets. Each data CSV file encapsulates a portion of the dataset by sorting them into ascending order and then splitting it, contributing to a modular and organized structure within the 'data' directory.

Name	Index
ABC	90
ABC	89
DEF	1
DEF	10
XYZ	102

Fig. 2. Top five rows of the first data csv file in the data folder

The index.csv file acts as a navigational guide, providing an indexed reference to the data spread across the various CSV files within the 'data' folder. This indexing mechanism facilitates seamless retrieval and analysis of specific data slices, enhancing the overall accessibility and usability of the dataset.

column	csv	low	high	type	indexes	count
Column1	Column1_PvCY.csv	ABVAAM	YcFcTpxw	object	[652, 108, 616, 709, 63	500
Column2	Column2_PeM.csv	YdijlLEM	zwZdT	object	[967, 959, 948, 802, 22	500
Column3	Column3_AtIE.csv	FALSE	TRUE	bool	[0, 546, 547, 548, 550,	500
Column4	Column4_tQp.csv	TRUE	TRUE	bool	[102, 792, 761, 958, 21	500
Column5	Column5_EYe.csv	1	50	int64	[819, 228, 798, 922, 73	500

Fig. 3. Top five rows of the index csv file in the data folder

The index csv file contains the following columns:

- column: This represents the column that csv represents
- csv: name of the csv file of that specify dataset
- low: the lowest value of that specific data file and type
- high: the highest value of that specific data file and type

- type: the data type of that column
- indexes: the indexes present in the dataset
- count: the number of data values included in the dataset

The number of data CSV files generated within the 'data' folder is contingent upon the size of the original dataset, denoted by 'n' rows and 'm' columns, as well as a user-defined split value referred to as the threshold 'T'. The calculation for determining the number of data CSV files can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{Number of data CSV files} = (n \times m) / T$$

This formula reflects the systematic approach undertaken by Splitflow to break down extensive datasets into manageable chunks, allowing for more efficient data processing and analysis. The user-defined threshold 'T' serves as a critical parameter in determining the granularity of the data subsets, affording users flexibility and control over the partitioning process. Consequently, this approach enhances the scalability of dataset management and ensures that users can adapt the framework to suit their specific computational and analytical requirements.

III. METHODOLOGY

Utilizing Splitflow involves a straightforward process, aligning with its column-oriented design. This section provides practical insights into employing the library for distributed dataframe analysis.

A. Installation and Initialization

Initiate the installation of Splitflow by employing standard Python package management. Utilize the 'pip' command in your terminal to install the library seamlessly:

```
pip install splitflow
```

To update Splitflow you must use the command in the terminal:

```
pip install splitflow --upgrade
```

Upon successful installation, import the library into your Python environment.

```
import splitflow
```

Then create an object to access all the methods that follow as following.

```
a=splitflow.SplitFlow()
```

where, *a* is the object

B. Loading data into the system

To incorporate Splitflow into your project for the first time, begin by loading your extensive CSV dataset

into the system. If your dataset is large, necessitating a conversion to the Splitflow data format with data organized within the 'data' folder, the load() method is vital for accomplishing this transformation.

Syntax:

```
load(data,thresh=100,index='index',dest='data')
```

where,

data=location of the large csv

thresh=the split value of the columns, the user needs to choose an optimal value that will provide the most efficient access time., the default value is 100

index= name of the index column in the file, if any. If not the algorithm will create one

dest= where the data folder will be located and the name of the folder.

If the 'data' folder is already established, it is imperative to establish a connection to the existing 'data' directory.

To connect to the data we use the connect() method.

Syntax:

connect(data='data',index='index')

where,

data= name and location of the data folder

index= name given to index folder during loading

When engaged in a data analysis project, it is essential to establish the data folder initially, ensuring it is created only once. Subsequently, this folder can be conveniently shared. We recommend compressing the data folder to expedite the sharing process and enable swift utilization of the data. This approach facilitates immediate connection and initiation of data analysis activities, especially considering that the loading phase may consume a significant amount of time, whereas the connection process is instantaneous.

C. Statistical Analysis

Perform statistical analyses on specific columns utilizing the mean(), mode(), and median() methods based

on [11]. This approach aids in comprehending the central tendency of our dataset, shedding light on where

the midpoint lies and providing insights into the prevailing values around which our dataset tends to cluster.

mean() to find the mean of a column:

Syntax:

mean(col)

where,*col*= column whose mean is to be calculated

mode() to find the mode of a column:

Syntax:

mode(col)

where,*col*= column whose mode is to be calculated

median() to find the median of a column:

Syntax:

median(col)

where,*col*= column whose median is to be calculated

All calculations and programming techniques must be explicitly tailored to individual columns, as the library is meticulously designed with a specific emphasis on column-centric operations. This ensures

precision and efficiency in handling data, promoting a targeted approach that aligns with each column's inherent structure and characteristics within the dataset.

D. Data Exploration

Explore data distribution and values within columns by employing functions such as `count()`, `value_counts()`, and `column_values()`. These functions assist in uncovering data frequencies, providing valuable insights to guide decision-making and strategic planning for further data handling.

`count()` to find the number of values in a column:

Syntax:

`count(col)`

where, *col*= column whose count is to understood

`value_count()` to find the number of each value present in a column:

Syntax:

`value_count(col)`

where, *col*= find the count of each value in the column

`column_values()` to get the values of a column:

Syntax:

`column_values(col)`

where, *col*= column whose values are to be returned

E. Data Retrieval

Efficiently retrieve specific data slices housed within the designated 'data' folder using the `index.csv` file generated through Splitflow. This file is a strategic guide, allowing for precise navigation and selecting targeted datasets based on specific criteria. By harnessing the power of the index, users gain a streamlined approach to accessing relevant data slices, enhancing the overall efficiency and precision of data retrieval processes within the Splitflow framework. This capability is invaluable in scenarios requiring nuanced analyses or focused investigations, providing an added layer of flexibility and value to the data management workflow.

`find()` to find the index of all values in the column which match requirement:

Syntax:

`find(col,relation=None,value=None)`

where,

col= columns whose index values are returned

value= value to which the value of the columns are compared based on which the corresponding index is

returned if the value of column is in proper relation to the value

relation= the determines what index should be returned based on whether the column value meets the relation to the value given,

the relation can take the following values:

- '*eq*': column value is equal to the value
- '*lt*': column value is less than equal to the value
- '*-lt*': column value is less than the value
- '*gt*': column value is greater than equal to the value
- '*-gt*': column value is greater than value

values() to get the values of a column at the given indexes:

Syntax:

values(col,indexes)

col= column whose values are returned as a list

indexes= value of the column on those indexes are returned, this function can be used with find() or with other functions to understand the data further.

F. Identifying Duplicates

Elevate your data analysis endeavours with the sophisticated capabilities of Splitflow, empowering you to seamlessly detect and conduct a comprehensive analysis of duplicate values within specified columns in your dataset. In the pursuit of refining your dataset and unravelling valuable insights, Splitflow offers indispensable methods, prominently including duplicates(), which play a pivotal role in enhancing the analytical depth and precision of your data management strategies.

duplicates: returns a dictionary of column values and their count, hence their duplicates

Syntax:

duplicates('col')

where,col- the column whose duplicate count is returned to understand the data

G. MapReduce Operations

In the course of data analysis, Splitflow offers users the ability to create customized functions tailored to their specific analytical needs. This functionality extends beyond the confines of pre-built methods, giving users the flexibility to craft bespoke analytical tools that align precisely with the intricacies and nuances of their dataset.

The user can use the MapRed() method and give it their functions to call.

MapRed():

Syntax:

MapRed(col,mapper,reducer)

Where,

col- the column on which the custom functions are applied

mapper- the custom function created by the user which is used on the split distributed datasets

reducer- the custom function created by the user, which is applied on the list returned after parallel processing to combine and produce the final output

This method is inspired by the MapReduce algorithm used in Big data technology [9] and [10].

Example of Mapreduce custom function:

In Splitflow's customizable distributed processing system, users can craft their own mapper and reducer functions. In this section, we delve into the creation of custom functions tailored for a specific task: determining the count of each value in a column, with a threshold set to 3 as an illustrative example for a single-column dataset, the dataset used in the example is a single column 11 row dataset with random strings in each row.

Mapper Function:

For the mapper function, the user's design should focus on processing each split data file independently and returning the value counts specific to that dataset. The algorithm for finding the count of values is outlined below

Algorithm for finding the count of values

1. Initialize an empty dictionary to store value counts.
2. Iterate elements in the list.
 - a. If the element is already a key in the dictionary, increment its value by 1.
 - b. If the element is not a key in the dictionary, add it as a key with a value of 1.
3. Iterate through the dictionary store the count for each unique value.

This mapper function ensures that each split dataset is processed independently, capturing the count of each unique value within the specified threshold. The above values will be added to the resultant list after the system passes the datasets through the mapper function parallelly.

Reducer Function:

For the reducer function, the user must design it to calculate the final answer from a list of sub-answers obtained from individual split datasets of that column. The algorithm for combining dictionary values, ensuring that the duplicate keys have their values summed and unique added, is outlined below

An algorithm for combining dictionary values such that the same keys will have the values added and unique keys will be included into the common dictionary:

1. Initialize an empty dictionary to store combined values `combined_dict`.
2. Iterate through each key-value pair in the original dictionary.
 - a. If the key is not in `combined_dict`, add it with its current value.
 - b. If the key is already in `combined_dict`, sum the existing value with the current value.
3. Print or store the combined dictionary.

Fig. 4. Representation of finding count of values using splitflow

IV. COMPARISON WITH EXISTING SOLUTIONS

Pandas[1], Polars[2], Dask[3], and Modin[4] are all popular Python libraries designed to handle and manipulate large datasets efficiently.

- Pandas:

Pandas are the most popularly used data manipulation libraries in Python. It provides data structures like DataFrames and Series, making it easy to work with tabular data. Pandas are efficient for small to

medium-sized datasets and are commonly used in data cleaning, exploration, and transformation tasks. It has comprehensive functionality for data manipulation and analysis.

- Polars:

Polars is a relatively newer library than Pandas but has gained attention for its high-performance DataFrame implementation. It is designed to be memory-efficient and fast, making it suitable for large-scale data processing. It has high performance due to a native Rust implementation. They are designed for parallel and multithreaded processing.

- Dask:

Dask is a parallel computing library that integrates with Pandas, Numpy [8], and other libraries to enable parallel and distributed computing for larger-than-memory datasets. Dask operates seamlessly with existing Python libraries and extends their capabilities to handle larger datasets that may not fit into memory. Scalability for working with larger-than-memory datasets. They distributed computing capabilities for clusters.

- Modin:

Modin is designed to accelerate Pandas operations by using parallel and distributed computing. It aims to seamlessly scale Pandas to handle larger datasets by utilizing the computing resources efficiently. Efficiently operates multicore systems to speed up data operations. Provides options for both single-node and distributed computing.

The following are comparative tests conducted to discern the varying performance using techniques in [5] of distinct libraries. For testing purposes, a custom CSV file was created and used; this CSV file contains ten columns and 1000 rows, and each column is of a random datatype.

Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7	Column8	Column9	Column10
TRUE	FALSE	wLrjlxXd	FALSE	52	64	77	vBQdfdna	30	62
TRUE	TRUE	FKRWIKwT	TRUE	93	98	30	memwVVw	82	74
FALSE	TRUE	fjFmMudE	TRUE	15	59	33	ZSXfMVEL	19	10
TRUE	FALSE	vbEboVZw	TRUE	72	56	77	DWWYFCy	31	72
FALSE	FALSE	ZSnfVdNS	TRUE	61	59	26	xHvYCwxy	60	54

Fig. 5. The first 5 rows of the custom dataset

Time comparisons for calculating the mean of a column:

Fig. 6. Time comparisons for calculating the mean of a column using different libraries

In Figure 5, the red bar represents the performance of Splitflow in comparison to the other libraries, depicted by the blue bars.

Time comparisons for calculating the mode of a column:

Fig. 7. Time comparisons for calculating the mode of a column using different libraries

In Figure 7, the red bar represents the performance of Splitflow in comparison to the other libraries, depicted by the blue bars.

Memory Usage comparisons:

Fig. 8. Memory Usage comparisons while using different libraries

In Figure 8, the red bar represents the Memory usage of Splitflow in comparison to the other libraries, depicted by the blue bars.

Data loading time:

Fig. 9. Loading time comparisons using different libraries

Figure 9 represents the total loading time of data up to a specified count, with the data being loaded 2000 times in the presented plot. The blue line depicts the actual time taken to load data using Splitflow. Splitflow initially exhibits a longer data loading time due to creating the data folder. However, after the initial setup, subsequent data loading operations demonstrate significantly quicker performance. As depicted in the graph, after 2000 loading instances, Splitflow achieves the lowest total loading time. Notably, if users share the data as the data folder, the initial loading time can be mitigated, enhancing the overall efficiency of subsequent loading operations.

V. USE CASES SCENARIO

a. Use Case Example 1:

A healthcare organization manages a vast repository of patient data, including medical records, diagnostic reports, and treatment histories. Analyzing this data is crucial for improving patient outcomes, identifying trends, and optimizing healthcare delivery. However, the sheer volume and complexity of healthcare data pose significant challenges for traditional data processing methods. The healthcare organization faces difficulties in efficiently analyzing large-scale patient datasets. Conventional dataframe processing tools struggle to handle the volume and diversity of healthcare data, leading to bottlenecks in data processing workflows. Moreover, the organization seeks to perform column-specific analyses to derive insights tailored to different medical parameters and patient demographics. To address these challenges, the healthcare organization adopts Splitflow.

How can Splitflow be used in this use case:

The healthcare organization receives large datasets containing patient information, including demographics, medical history, and treatment records. Splitflow's built-in methods such as `mean()`, `mode()`, and `median()` are employed to compute statistical measures for medical parameters such as blood pressure, cholesterol levels, and glucose levels. The organization conducts exploratory data analysis to identify trends, patterns, and outliers in patient health metrics. Splitflow enables the organization to segment patients based on specific medical conditions, demographic characteristics, or treatment outcomes. Custom MapReduce operations are applied to aggregate and summarize patient data, facilitating targeted interventions and personalized healthcare approaches. Leveraging Splitflow's efficient data processing capabilities, the organization derives actionable insights to improve patient care, optimize treatment protocols, and enhance healthcare outcomes. Decision-makers utilize the analyzed data to implement evidence-based practices, allocate resources effectively, and drive organizational strategies.

Benefits of using Splitflow:

Splitflow streamlines healthcare data processing, reducing the time and resources required for analysis. Column-specific analyses enable the organization to derive targeted insights, leading to more informed decision-making. Splitflow's distributed processing capabilities allow the organization to scale seamlessly with growing datasets and evolving analytical needs.

b. Use Case Example 2:

A financial institution manages extensive datasets containing transaction records, customer profiles, and market data. Analyzing this data is crucial for detecting fraudulent activities, optimizing investment strategies, and improving risk management practices. However, traditional data processing methods struggle to handle the volume and complexity of financial data efficiently. The financial institution faces challenges in processing and analyzing large-scale

financial datasets promptly. Conventional dataframe processing tools lack the scalability and performance required to handle the intricacies of financial data analysis, leading to delays in decision-making and increased operational risks. To address these challenges, the financial institution adopts Splitflow. Splitflow's column-oriented approach and efficient data segmentation capabilities make it well-suited for processing large-scale financial datasets. By leveraging Splitflow's functionalities, the institution aims to streamline financial data analysis and derive actionable insights to enhance risk management and investment decision-making processes.

How can Splitflow be used in this use case:

Statistical analyses, such as mean transaction values and transaction frequency, are computed using Splitflow's built-in methods. Splitflow enables the institution to analyze historical market data and identify potential risk factors using advanced statistical models. Custom MapReduce operations are applied to aggregate and summarize risk metrics, facilitating real-time risk monitoring and mitigation. Splitflow's column-specific functions are utilized to analyze market trends, identify investment opportunities, and optimize portfolio allocations. Machine learning models are trained using Splitflow-preprocessed data to forecast market trends and optimize investment strategies.

Benefits of using Splitflow:

Splitflow streamlines financial data processing, reducing analysis time and enabling faster decision-making. Column-specific analyses enable the institution to derive targeted insights, leading to more informed risk management and investment decisions. Splitflow's distributed processing capabilities allow the institution to scale seamlessly with growing datasets and evolving analytical needs.

c. Use Case Example 3:

A small business owner manages a shop and aims to leverage social media platforms for marketing and customer engagement. Analyzing social media data, including user interactions, post engagement, and customer feedback, is essential for understanding customer preferences and optimizing marketing strategies. However, the owner faces challenges in processing and analyzing social media data efficiently due to limited resources and technical expertise. The small business owner struggles to analyze social media data effectively using traditional data processing methods, which often require manual data manipulation and lack scalability. Limited time and resources hinder the owner's ability to derive actionable insights from social media analytics, leading to missed opportunities for customer engagement and growth. To address these challenges, the small business owner adopts Splitflow. Splitflow's intuitive methods and column-oriented approach make it accessible and easy to use for users with limited technical expertise. By leveraging Splitflow's functionalities, the owner aims to streamline social media analytics workflows, derive actionable insights from social media data, and enhance customer engagement strategies.

How can Splitflow be used in this use case:

The small business owner uses Splitflow to preprocess social media data, including user comments, likes, shares, and post engagement metrics. Splitflow's built-in methods such as `mean()`, `mode()`, and `count()` are utilized to compute statistical measures for post engagement, user interactions, and customer sentiment. Custom MapReduce operations are applied to aggregate and summarize engagement data, facilitating insights into effective content strategies and audience

preferences.

Benefits of using Splitflow:

Splitflow simplifies social media data processing, allowing the small business owner to analyze large volumes of data quickly and accurately. Splitflow's column-oriented approach enables the owner to derive actionable insights from social media analytics, such as identifying popular content, understanding customer sentiment, and optimizing marketing strategies. Splitflow's user-friendly methods and affordability make it an ideal solution for small businesses with limited resources, providing powerful data analytics capabilities without the need for extensive technical expertise or investment in expensive software.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper thoroughly explores Splitflow, a Python library designed for distributed dataframe processing. Splitflow's column-oriented approach, showcased in its architecture, provides an efficient way to handle large datasets. The library's numerous methods, focusing on column-specific operations, make it versatile for various data analytics tasks. Performance evaluation demonstrates Splitflow's efficiency, scalability, and resource utilization. Comparative analyses with pandas, polars, dask, and Modin highlight Splitflow areas for potential optimization. While Splitflow shows promising performance, ongoing development, community engagement, and optimizations can further enhance its capabilities in the distributed dataframe processing domain.

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